

PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION AT TASHKENT STATE UNIVERSITY OF LAW

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ABSTRACT

The formation of physical culture and sports through classes in one or more sports allows to reveal and realize the real and potential capabilities of students, is a promising means of introducing them to physical culture and sports activities, as well as a healthy lifestyle.

Relevance: The formation of physical culture and sports, increasing the level of physical fitness of students, as well as systematic sports are important components of the competitiveness of the younger generation in modern life and are the main criteria at all age stages of its development. At the same time, the deterioration of the state of health and the level of physical fitness of students in the conditions of social, economic and environmental problems indicates the need to correct the existing traditional approach in physical education of students at the University. The lack of the necessary motivation for the majority of students to engage in physical exercises further aggravates the situation.

Based on the above, the problem of activation of motor activity and the formation of stable motivation of students

to engage in physical culture and sports at the University is brewing.

The analysis of recent studies reveals that in most universities, the organization of the physical education process and the distribution of students into training groups take place without taking into account the interests and needs in the motor activity of the students themselves, which leads to a decrease in motivation and is often accompanied by a deterioration in the dynamics of motor fitness. In this regard, the number of missed classes without valid reasons and due to illness increases, which in turn significantly reduces the overall performance of students and the quality of physical training.

The problems related to the formation of physical culture and sports of students at the University were studied by N.P. Abalakova (2001), V.K. Balsevich (2003), N.I. Volkov (1967), V.M. Zatsiorsky (1970),

V.S. Kuznetsov (2000), P. Kunat (1973), L.P. Matveev (1977), M.Ya. Nabatnikov (1982), etc.

It should be noted that there are quite a lot of reasons for the negative impact on the indicators of physical fitness of students - this is a decrease in the standard of living, deterioration of working and recreation conditions, the state of the environment, the quality and structure of nutrition.

The objective of this study is to increase the motivation to engage in physical exercises of a certain orientation of students at Tashkent State University of Law, using the example of athletics, as well as to identify positive dynamics in improving the individual motor capabilities of the University's students.

Studying at a university is an important stage in the formation of a future specialist, acquiring not only special knowledge, but also understanding the meaning of physical education, the ethics of physical exercises, knowledge of the basics of sports hygiene, developing stable habits for regular physical exercises.

Studies conducted at the Tashkent State University of Law show that for the majority of graduate specialties, such physical qualities as endurance, speed and strength are professionally important. Much attention is paid to the development of these qualities in physical education classes at the University.

Endurance is the only physical quality that has a direct dependence on the state of the cardiovascular and respiratory system of the body. Mental and physical performance is closely related to endurance. Speed is directly interrelated with professional readiness, since the level of its development affects the mobility of nervous processes, mental performance

and efficiency of thinking. Muscle strength is related to the functions of organs and systems of the human body, with its emotions and energy. A trained muscular apparatus has more opportunities to protect the entire human body from the harmful effects of educational and industrial activities.

For the education of these professionally important qualities, such sports as athletics, sports games, etc. have the greatest opportunities.

At the beginning of the educational process, students were given the opportunity to decide on the choice of a specific sport or any system of physical exercises for regular classes during their studies at the University. At the introductory classes, a questionnaire was conducted with students on the topic: "Students' attitude to physical education and sports". To the question, "What kind of sport would you prefer to do at a University?", 72% of respondents chose athletics.

Athletics is one of the most popular sports that contributes to the comprehensive development of a person, as it combines common, necessary and vital movements. Systematic training in athletics exercises develops speed, endurance, strength and other qualities necessary for a person in everyday life.

Athletics occupies a central place in the system of physical education due to its diversity, accessibility, dosage, as well as its applied value.

An experimental group of 24 people was formed from those who wanted to do athletics. The control group consisted of students who attended classes according to the general program.

In the educational and training process, the following tasks were solved: harmonious physical development of students, versatile training, as well as strengthening the state of health.

When building the training process, we were guided by the following principles:

- target orientation;
- proportionality in the development of basic physical qualities;
- the leading factors determining the level of skill development.

To solve the tasks, the following research methods were used: analysis and generalization of scientific and methodological literature; pedagogical observations; pedagogical experiment; methods for assessing the control of physical fitness of students; questionnaires; statistical analysis of the results of an experimental study.

To assess and control the physical fitness of students, the following physical fitness tests were used: running 100 m (boys and girls); long jump from a place (boys and girls); push-ups on the uneven bars (boys); lifting the torso from a supine position (girls); running 3000 m (boys) and 2000 m (girls).

The educational and training process was considered as an integral dynamic system, where specific tasks for the development of motor qualities, methods and values of training effects were solved at each specific stage. It was organized in accordance with certain target tasks, which were specifically expressed by the magnitude of the predicted result and conditioned the necessary implementation of the program of the training process. The entire training process consisted of several stages and was interconnected with the

year-round period of study at the University.

At the first stage, a medical and pedagogical examination was carried out. It was important to determine the capabilities of students, as a coach-teacher needs to know his/her students, their character inclinations, study conditions, life. Only students who had no deviations in health, physical development and functional fitness, as well as persons with minor, more often functional deviations, but not lagging behind in their physical development and functional fitness, were allowed to participate in athletics.

At the second stage of training, the tasks were set - strengthening health, comprehensive physical development, training in various physical exercises and instilling interest in athletics. Anthropometric measurements were carried out every three months before the start of the training year and the following ones.

The third stage- the stage of an in-depth training process, was aimed at creating the necessary prerequisites for extremely intense training in order to maximize the realization of individual capabilities. All the work was aimed at forming the foundation of special preparedness of students, as well as at developing sustainable motivation to achieve significant results.

The results of the study indicate an increase in all indicators of physical fitness in the experimental group. The physical fitness of the boys of the experimental group I and II courses increased by 13.1% (average value). While in the boys of the control group only - by 3% (average value). In the girls of the experimental group I and II courses, the indicators of physical fitness

improved by 9.1% (average value); in the girls of the control group - by 3% (average value). (Table 1-2).

Table 1.
Dynamics of physical fitness indicators of young men (I and II courses).

control exercises	Group	I-II courses, 2018				Growth, %
		February	May	September	November	
running 100 m, sec.	e	13,6±0,1	13,3±0,1	13,4±0,1	13,2±0,1	2,9
	c	14,0±0,1	13,9±0,1	14,0±0,1	13,9±0,1	0,7
long jump from a place, cm	e	233±2	244±2	243±2	251±2	7,7
	c	226±2	230±2	231±2	234±2	3,5
push-ups on the uneven bars, (number of times)	e	16±1	20±1	19±1	22±1	37,5
	c	14±1	15±1	14±1	15±1	7,1
running 3000 m, min/sec.	e	12.31±0.05	12.09±0.05	12.14±0.05	11.58±0.05	4,3
	c	12.36±0.05	12.29±0.05	12.36±0.05	12.30±0.05	0,7

Table 2.
Dynamics of physical fitness indicators of young women (I and II courses).

control exercises	Group	I-II courses, 2018				Growth, %
		February	May	September	November	
running 100 m, sec.	e	16,1±0,1	15,7±0,1	15,7±0,1	15,6±0,1	3,1
	c	17,6±0,1	17,4±0,1	17,5±0,1	17,5M	0,5
long jump from a place, cm	e	166±2	172±2	174±2	179±2	7,8
	c	157±2	160±2	160±2	163±2	3,8

lifting the trunk from the supine position (number of times)	e	31±1	35±1	36±1	38±1	22,5
	c	28±1	29±1	30±1	30±1	7,1
running 2000 m, min/sec.	e	12.18±0.05	12.01±0.05	12.04±0.05	11.53±0.05	3,3
	c	12.46±0.05	12.42±0.05	12.44±0.05	12.39±0.05	0,9

In Tables 1-2: e – experimental group; c – control group.

Conclusions:

1. The results of the study showed significant increases in the physical fitness of students of the experimental group in comparison with the control group.
2. Students who regularly attend classes in the discipline "physical education and sports", engage in physical exercises of a certain orientation and do not interrupt classes even during intermediate control tests in special subjects, pass the period of student life more safely for their health.

3. In addition, among students engaged in physical exercises of a certain orientation, there is a more rational use of time during the day, unlike students engaged in a standard program. This provides a basis to recommend the organization of physical education at the University, taking into account the interests and needs of students in motor activity of a certain orientation, increasing motivation and improving the dynamics of students' preparedness.

REFERENCES:

1. Vilensky M.Ya. Physical culture in the scientific organization of students' educational work. M: Prometheus, 1993, p. 156.
2. Krucevich T.Yu. Theory and methodology of physical education: in 2 volumes. Vol. 1: General foundations of the theory and methodology of physical education: textbook for universities of physical education // Olympic literature 2003, p. 424.
3. Orlan I.V. Methodology of physical education of students of the main department of universities on the basis of sports-oriented problem-modular teaching technology: Dissertation, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Volgograd, 2002, p. 172.
4. Shapovalenko I.V. Age psychology (Developmental psychology and age psychology): a textbook for universities. M: Gardariki, 2007. p. 349.
5. Verkhorubova O. V., Podlesskaya O. S. The problem of formation of health culture among students // Bulletin of Tomsk State Pedagogical University. 2013. Issue 4 (132). p. 148-150.